

Interview Form: Bug Reproduction and Application Monitoring at Lentune Ltd.

Section 1: General Information

Please fill in your details below.

1. Interviewee Name: _____
2. Position/Role: _____
3. Department: _____
4. Software Engineering Experience: _____
5. Experience with Bug Reproduction: _____
6. Role in Bug Reproduction Process: _____

Section 2: Experience with Current Bug Reproduction Process

1. Can you describe the current bug reproduction process at Lentune?

2. What are the main challenges you face with the current bug reproduction process?

3. How effective do you find the current bug reproduction process in identifying and resolving issues?

4. Are there any specific tools or methods you currently use to aid in bug reproduction? If yes, please specify.

Section 3: System Usability

1. Do you use the Application Performance Monitoring (APM) system often?

Yes No

2. On a scale of 1-7, how user-friendly do you find the APM system in the context of bug report reproduction? Why?

Rating: 1 (Not at all) to 7 (Extremely user-friendly)

Reason:

3. What specific features of the APM system do you find most helpful for bug reproduction?

4. Are there any features you find difficult to use or understand? Please specify.

Section 4: System Performance

1. Does the APM system capture relevant data for bug reproduction?

Always captures relevant data

Mostly captures relevant data

Occasionally misses relevant data

Frequently misses relevant data

2. Have you experienced any performance issues with the APM system (e.g., slow response times, system crashes) that impact bug reproduction? If yes, please describe.

Section 5: Monitoring Capabilities

1. What types of metrics and logs does the APM system track that are useful for bug reproduction? (e.g., CPU usage, memory usage, network traffic, error logs)

2. How comprehensive do you find the system's monitoring capabilities for capturing data relevant to bug reproduction?

Extremely comprehensive

Very comprehensive

Moderately comprehensive

Slightly comprehensive

Not at all comprehensive

3. Can the system monitor all critical data relevant to bug reproduction? If not, which data are missing?

Section 6: Integration and Compatibility

1. Does the APM system integrate well with other tools and systems you use for bug tracking and reproduction? If yes, please list them. If no, what is missing?

2. Have you encountered any compatibility issues with the APM system and your applications or infrastructure that affect bug reproduction? Please describe.

3. How easy is it to integrate new components of the software into the monitoring system for the purpose of bug reproduction? (Only for developers)

Section 7: Overall Satisfaction

1. Overall, how satisfied are you with the APM system for aiding in bug report reproduction? Why?

Very satisfied

Satisfied

Neutral

Unsatisfied

Very unsatisfied

2. What are the main strengths of the APM system in the context of bug reproduction?

3. What areas do you believe need improvement for better bug reproduction?

4. Would you continue using the APM system for bug reproduction? Why or why not?

Section 8: Additional Comments

1. Do you have any additional feedback or suggestions for improving the APM system specifically for bug reproduction?
